

Single Contract Power Optimization: A Novel Business Model for Smart Buildings Using Intelligent Energy Management

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Abstract

Typically, residential buildings neither allow flexibility in the individual contract power capacity nor considers buildings as unique electricity consumers. In this work, a smart building is designed that each electricity customer has flexible contract power and the whole collective residential building has a single contract power. A management entity is considered to manage all energy resources of the building such as the photovoltaic generation, electric vehicles, and battery energy storage system, taking into consideration the consumption from apartments and common services, to minimize the electricity bill. Hence, the best/optimal contract power capacity will contribute to minimizing electricity costs. Therefore, finding the optimal decision of the contract power value has received a significant role from the energy management in smart buildings. In this paper, a mixed binary optimization problem is formulated in which not only the optimal value of contract power is yield but the optimal schedule of the electric vehicle/battery storage charge and discharge are found, taking into consideration the photovoltaic generation and load consumption profiles. The proposed model is implemented for three scenarios, and the obtained results show that the model efficiency has a high performance with a significant electricity cost reduction, around 47%. The results pointed that using an optimal value of single contract power and intelligent management system, the building electricity costs decrease remarkably.

Keywords: Smart Building, Energy Management, Mixed Binary Linear Programming, Optimal contract power, Renewable Energy, Mathematical Modeling

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the use of electricity has increased and the demand for electricity in developing countries, in particular, is expected to increase rapidly in line with economic and population growth [1]. Furthermore, concerns with carbon dioxide and greenhouse gas emissions have arisen and have inspired governments and researchers to concentrate on designing smart buildings and home energy management systems using renewable energy sources [2]. Therefore, the design and operation of systems that incorporate significant shares of volatile renewable energy, while improving overall system performance, is a pressing task for future energy systems [3]. A good understanding of the existence and structure of the use of energy in buildings is therefore essential for the development of adequate future policies on energy and climate change. To allow a comprehensive review, the availability of updated data is becoming increasingly necessary [4]. Electricity monitoring that gathers the consumption and generation data is crucial for the deployment of energy management techniques, to reduce electricity costs and contribute to a cleaner and sustainable environment.

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The electricity charge is a major part of residential building costs. This paper aims to investigate and discuss an approach to reduce the energy bill in collective residential buildings. Typically, an electricity invoice includes the costs regarding Contract Power (CP) value, active (and reactive, depending on consumer's type) energy consumed, taxes, and other costs [5]. Via contracted power capacity, utility companies impose a maximum consumption limit on each of their consumers, by establishing an individual electricity supply contract, without any flexibility on that CP capacity. Usually, electricity tariffs can be different depending on the time-of-use (that is the time of the day: peak, half peak, normal off-peak and super off-peak hours), daily or weekly-cycle and also the season of the year [6]. Typically, in Low Voltage (LV), there are many CP options, usually at predefined power levels, so that a consumer can select one of them according to their electricity needs (single-phase, three-phase, number of housing compartments, and type of loads)[7].

In this paper, it is proposed an energy resources management (ERM) approach for a multi-unit residential building towards to the energy efficiency usage and electricity reduction costs. In this approach, it is considered to have flexibility in customers contracted power value. In legal terms, LV consumers must have necessarily a contracted power. This model proposes an innovative concept to be applied on collective residential buildings, as it proposes a single electricity contract for the whole building and the existence of a management entity responsible, simultaneously, for electricity trade among consumers and the management of the building energy resources. A new player emerges with the responsibility to manage all the building energy resources and optimizing a single electricity contract from an external power network. Indeed, the proposed approach addresses a knowledge gap that may be used in collective residential buildings, by considering the energy resources management and the building as a single electricity consumer. The results showed the efficiency of the method and can open new opportunities and business plans.

A case study is deployed considering a residential building with 15 apartments, common areas and a garage. The residential building is equipped with rooftop photovoltaic (PV) systems, battery energy storage system (BESS), and intensive use of Electric Vehicles (EVs). Three use cases were considered: In case I, a "traditional multi-unit residential building" without any smartness (energy management) is considered. In this case, no optimization is applied and the electricity cost of each apartment is calculated, straightforwardly. In case II, an energy management approach is considered to schedule and dispatch power among external power network, residential apartments, PVs, and EVs. A single contract power is considered to supply the entire building. In this case, the main goal is to minimize the total building electricity cost by determining an optimal CP capacity and optimizing the schedule of EVs charging/discharging process. To attain this aim, a Mixed Binary Linear Programming (MBLP) model was formulated, such that its solution provides a recipe for the managing entity to control the power dispatch among building resources. Case III is similar to case II, but a BESS is considered to guarantee and exploit better management of the energy resources in the residential building.

The remaining of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 a short review of energy management systems of buildings is presented. Section 3 addresses the problem description. In Section 4 the proposed methodology and model development are presented. In Section 5 a case study using real data is presented. The last section summarizes the concluding remarks.

2. SHORT LITERATURE REVIEW

Energy management systems solutions are a powerful tool for building to manage electrical energy efficiently. Residential buildings may contain several energy resources such as photovoltaic generation panels, energy storage systems, and electrical vehicles. Demand response programs can be also considered as a resource that consumers' aggregators can use as an energy-efficient management method [8], to manage the daily energy exchanges in smart building (SB) or within a community of SB [9].

Indeed, several research works were developed to size the optimal capacity of energy storage systems to smooth consumption peaks. For instance, Reference [10] used the Taiwan Power Company System as an example system to test an algorithm to evaluate the economic benefit of battery energy storage. The size of BESS capacity is also explored for industrial customers' use, as presented in Reference [11], in which the

60 maximum economic benefits of BESS were properly estimated. However, the application of BESS in the context of residential buildings can be promising to smooth out peak consumption and contribute to an increase in energy efficiency. The integration of a renewable generation system with a BESS can boost energy efficiency in buildings. In Reference [12], an electricity management model was proposed that allows residential customers to save a considerable portion of their bill by reducing contractual capacity and using a BESS. The impact of the EV in buildings is also a relevant topic in the context of energy management. For instance, Reference [13] discusses the impact of the charging of the EV, in which their results indicate that the proposed load control and the implementation of PV generation allow decreasing the peak load. In Reference [14], the energy demand of the private transport sector and building sector (with intensive use of EVs) is managed. The results showed a significant reduction in primary energy consumption and carbon dioxide emissions.

70 In Reference [15], an energy management system is proposed to reduce the power demands and energy costs of a residential building. The resources include the use of PV generation, BESS, and the schedule of EV's charging and discharging process. Results pointed to a 65% reduction in peak load consumption and a nearby 30% reduction in electricity consumption costs. In Reference [16], a mathematical model for efficient energy management of a residential building is proposed. The residential building includes various appliances such as energy storage systems, energy production systems (PV's) and smart meters, and two-way communication links between these components. A model predictive control is used to assess the optimum dispatch of different energy resources to meet the demand of a residential building while meeting the comfort level of customers. Simulation results showed that it was possible to reduce the energy bill and energy usage by 17% and 8%, respectively, over a day, by optimally managing all the resources. In Reference [17] a multi-objective mixed-binary linear programming is proposed that the scheduling of the charging and discharging process for EVs and BESS are obtained to minimize the total cost and peak load simultaneously. In order to find the Pareto front solutions, the authors applied the Pascoletti-Serafini scalarization approach. In this work, a fixed value of contract power was considered.

85 In Reference [18] a model to identify the optimal mix of renewable energy (RE) is developed. A structure for designing an integrated hybrid RE system at the building level was proposed, taking into consideration the minimization of energy system cost and the life cycle environmental impacts, maximizing operational cost savings and the RE fraction. Results pointed that Solar PV and ground source heat pumps were the recommended RE technologies for multi-unit residential buildings. The optimal energy system combination supplied 44% of the building's energy demand through RE. However, and at the building level, authors have identified that reaching net-zero status is not a feasible goal with the current resource potential and economic conditions. Therefore, significant emissions and operational cost reductions were achieved, mainly overall life cycle impacts were reduced by 11.4%, and annual carbon emissions can be reduced by 21.70%. In Reference [19], a Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) is used to optimize the design and scheduling operation of renewable energies in microgrids. This model provides a methodological framework for detailed planning and scheduling of energy microgrids. by considering the relevant price signals and potential risks.

90 The value of the contracted power is one of the parameters contained in the electricity bill and it is used as a way to limit the power purchase of the LV customers. Therefore, finding the optimal decision of the CP may have a significant role to reduce total cost in SB.

100 Some research works were developed to find the CP capacity, most of them were implemented for industrial customers. In Reference [20], the main goal was to optimize the contract capacity to minimize annual bill for industrial customers based on an evolutionary programming approach. This method helps users to optimize contract capacities, respectively, for peak, semi-peak, and off-peak loads.

105 In Reference [21], an algorithm was implemented to solve the contracted capacity (CC) optimization problem for most electrical consumers, typically medium and high voltage consumers, in Singapore. The number of months that their maximum demands exceed the optimal CC was calculated as well as the best CC.

In Reference [22], the optimal monthly contract capacity was determined to minimize the total cost of the electricity bill. It was proposed a linear programming formulation consisting of four elements: capacity charge, power factor adjustment, expanding construction charge, and disallowed decrease in contract capacities. The

implemented model was able to identify the time point when a contract capacity should be changed. The authors identified that customers with high off-peak loads should evaluate whether an off-peak contract capacity would minimize their electricity bill.

The schedule of renewable energy sources in the energy management of residential buildings is holding researchers' attention. In Reference [23], a MILP for a smart home's optimal energy management is implemented. The obtained results pointed that the availability of renewable sources had a significant impact on the optimal demand, BESS, and EVs charging/discharging process. In Reference [24], a MILP model is proposed to explore the cooperative evaluation of an energy management system operation in a building context, by considering the bidirectional energy trading of an EV, the effect of the PV uncertainty, and the impact of selling energy from the energy resources to the external grid on the total cost. In Reference [25] a survey offers a detailed overview of recent research related to optimization and simulation in power systems. Adequate models and tools to address uncertainty in energy scheduling strategies are crucial to deal with emerging resources such as EVs or renewable generation. The survey concludes that the study of the integration of renewable generation, demand response, EVs, or even aggregators are still very poor.

In Reference [26] a Consumer-Dependent Energy Management System was proposed for smart buildings. The main goal was to find a trade-off between the energy cost, either renewable or non-renewable and its carbon impact. The results pointed that it was possible to reduce costs by 7.3% and CO2 emission by 55.7%.

Studies concerning scheduling optimization for minimizing the energy demand of a building using EVs are very explored and widespread. In [27], a MILP model was implemented to optimize the control of the charging/discharging schedule EVs arriving at university buildings to minimize electricity costs. In [28], an optimization MILP model is proposed to evaluate the impact of the EVs charging stations as a flexible load to find the optimal schedule of BESS. Other approaches explore the possibility to decrease electricity cost-shifting loads from peak hours to off-peak hours by charging-discharging EVs properly conjugated with a BESS [29].

Indeed, the majority of works in the scope of resource management in buildings are mainly focused on minimizing costs with electricity consumption, smoothing peak consumption, choosing the best renewable technology, CP optimization (namely for industrial consumers), and the exploration of BESS and EVs as support for consumption management and costs reduction.

This proposed work differs from the state-of-the-art since then includes in the same work approaches that are usually addressed in a dispersed way, such as:

- Explores the CP flexibility, considering for that a single contract for the purchase of electricity for whole residential building;
- Implementation of an intelligent Energy Management System (EMS), responsible to manage the building energy resources (PV, EVs, BESS);
- Single contract power optimization for multi-unit residential building;
- Evaluation and comparison of electricity costs (before and after the EMS) for every single consumer (each apartment).

3. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

In this work, a residential smart building that contains J apartments and a common service is considered, where each apartment is equipped with a PV solar panel, installed on the rooftop of the building, and an Electrical Vehicle. Here, it is assumed that each EV has a unique daily use, and as soon as arrives, it is plugged into the building power infrastructures. Besides, EVs have bidirectional embedded chargers, such that their storage can be charged or discharged. However, both the charging and discharging process could not occur at the same time. The generated power by renewable sources (photovoltaic panels) is used to supply apartment load demand, charging the EVs batteries and, sell the surplus energy to the external power grid.

The total power cost of each consumer is based on the amount of consumed energy from the external grid, the amount of extra injected energy to the grid, and the contract power, which defines the tariff of consumed and injected energy at different times. There are some options for CP, such that a consumer can select one of them. Typically, the value of the contracted power is defined by power levels and defines the maximum amount of electricity that an electrical installation can receive. This implies that each consumer cannot consume more than the total value of the contracted power capacity. This value must be adapted to the consumer real needs, in terms of electrical power, to each type of consumer and respective consumption load profile.

Traditionally, each apartment has its contract power, and EVs are plugged in and charged as soon as arrive home. This scenario increases the electricity bill of apartments, since, there is no schedule on the EVs charge. An incorrect or inappropriate CP value may be inadvertently chosen by customers, which will impose an additional and unnecessary charge on the electricity bill. Accordingly, scheduling the charging time of EVs and choosing the optimal choice of CP will improve the electricity bill. Thus, and aiming to improve the electricity bill, the proposed approach takes into consideration the following requirements:

- Consideration of a single CP for the whole building;
- Flexible CP per each electrical customer;
- Centralizing the discharge process for EVs' battery in peak hours;
- Centralizing the charging/discharging schedule of EVs;
- Provide the use of BESS to explore the management of the building energy resources.

To consider these points, a building energy management is required. In this proposed approach a new player emerges: the energy building manager entity (which can be an aggregator, an electricity supplier, etc.). This player will be responsible to manage all the building energy resources to minimize the total building electricity costs. This approach, also considers that all tenants should agree to participate in this management ruled by this new player. The building is, therefore, seen as a whole and not being considered as having several autonomous electricity units.

To investigate the efficiency of the proposed approach, three cases were considered: in Case I, the traditional manner is considered that is called Non-Smart Management (NSM). The above idea without using BESS is considered in Case II that is called Smart Management with a Single Contract Power (SMSCP). Whereas, in Case III, a BESS is also used and is called Smart Management with a Single Contract Power and using BESS (SMSCP-B). In what follows, the details of each case are discussed and the mathematical model for case II and case III are considered.

4. METHODOLOGY AND MODELS DEVELOPMENT

In this sections the proposed methodology, the model that was developed as well as the obtained results are presented and discussed.

4.1. Case I: Non-Smart Management (NSM)

The NSM case (reference case) considers the residential building provided with individual PV generation (a PV generation per each electrical facility), Electrical Vehicles (EVs) usage but there is not an energy management system applied. The following points were taken into consideration:

- Each apartment has its contract power capacity with an external power grid (electricity supplier). The CP value of each apartment and common services are known;
- Each apartment has its PV system and the generated power can be consumed in its corresponding apartment;

- Each apartment has an EV and each EV is charged as soon as arrives in the building. The discharging of EVs is not considered;
- A Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) is not considered.

Note that the NSM case can be seen as a “traditional scenario” and the optimization formulation is not considered.

4.2. Case II: Smart Management with a Single Contract Power (SMSCP)

In the case SMSCP, it was considered the following requirements:

- An external entity (managing entity, aggregator, electricity supplier, etc.) is considered to manage all building energy resources. This entity is not only technically responsible for the building management resources but is also commercially responsible for all exchanges of electricity between the building and the external power network, as well as with each electricity consumer;
- All customers of the building agree to enter into a contract to purchase electricity from a single entity;
- There is no CP per apartment. That is, it is verified a flexible contracted power per each apartment. Only the existing electrical infrastructures limit the power used by each consumer;
- The residential building has just one contracted power from an external power network. The managing entity is responsible to optimize the single contract power of the residential building;
- The generated renewable energy from PVs panels is managed among apartments;
- Charging/discharging of EVs is managed by managing entity;
- The battery of an EV can charge/discharge to its corresponding apartment;
- The use of a BESS is not considered in this case.

The main aim of this case SMSCP is to present an energy schedule such that the building’s load demand can be fulfilled and electricity cost minimized. The mathematical formulation for Case SMSCP is presented in the next subsection 4.2.1.

4.2.1. Mathematical Models of Case SMSCP

In the SMSCP case, the EV charge/discharge optimization process is considered and presented. For this, the problem is modeled considering two distinct steps. In step (i), the total cost of the building’s electricity consumption is minimized. To this end, the optimization problem is solved and the total electricity cost is obtained. In step (ii), the electricity consumption cost per apartment is determined. The share of each apartment in the total cost is also determined.

(a): Step (i): Mathematical Model approach of Case II

In this subsection, the state problem in the SMSCP case is mathematically formulated by Mixed Binary Linear Problem (MBLP). In this regard, it is assumed that the considering time-period contains D day(s) and each day is divided into some step-times with duration τ . Moreover, the number of all time-steps is denoted by I and the number of EVs is denoted by J .

To develop the proposed model, the needed sets, parameters, and decision variables are presented and scripted in Tables 1, 2, and 3.

Note that, the index $d \in \mathbb{D}$ stands for index of days. For instance, the arrival time-step in d -th day is denoted by $T_{EV}^{in}(d, j)$ for $d \in \mathbb{D}$. And also, $d = 0$ and $d = D + 1$ are considered for the beginning and end times of the considered time-period. To make a better sense of the role of parameters, see Figure 1.

Table 1: Case II: List of sets.

Symbol	Set	Running Index	Description
\mathbb{I}	$\{1, \dots, I\}$	i	Set of time-step numbers
\mathbb{J}	$\{1, \dots, J\}$	j	Set of Vehicle numbers
\mathbb{D}	$\{1, \dots, D\}$	d	Set of day numbers

Table 2: Case II: Parameters.

Parameter	Index	Description
D		Number of days per time-study
I		Number of time-steps per time-study
τ		Time-step duration (hour)
J		Number of apartments (or EVs) in the building
$P_A(i, j)$	$i \in \mathbb{I}, j \in \mathbb{J}$	The total power demand of SB at period i
$P_C(i)$	$i \in \mathbb{I}$	The total power demand of common service at period i
$P_{PV}(i, j)$	$i \in \mathbb{I}, j \in \mathbb{J}$	Total generated power by PVs at period i
$T_{EV}^{in}(d, j)$	$j \in \mathbb{J}, d \in \{0\} \cup \mathbb{D}$	For $d = 0$, $T_{EV}^{in}(d, j) = 1$ and for $d \in \mathbb{D}$, $T_{EV}^{in}(d, j)$ is the number of period-time in which j th EV arrives at the parking in day d
$T_{EV}^{out}(d, j)$	$j \in \mathbb{J}, d \in \mathbb{D} \cup \{D+1\}$	For $d \in \mathbb{D}$, $T_{EV}^{out}(D+1, j)$ is the number of period-time in which the j th EV leaves in day d and for $d = D+1$, $T_{EV}^{out}(d, j) = I+1$
$S_{EV}^{max}(j)$	$j \in \mathbb{J}$	Maximum allowable State of Charge(SoC) of j th EV
$S_{EV}^{initial}(d, j)$	$j \in \mathbb{J}, d \in \{0\} \cup \mathbb{D}$	The initial SoC of j th EV at the beginning departure in time period $T_{EV}^{in}(d, j)$
$S_{EV}^{min_out}(d, j)$	$j \in \mathbb{J}, d \in \mathbb{D}$	The minimum allowable SoC for j th EV at exit time of each day d
$P_{EV}^{ch}(j)$	$j \in \mathbb{J}$	Active power related to the charging process of the j th EV
$P_{EV}^{diss}(j)$	$j \in \mathbb{J}$	Active power related to the discharging process of the j th EV
$E_{EV}^{ch}(j)$	$j \in \mathbb{J}$	The charge efficiency of EV j
$E_{EV}^{diss}(j)$	$j \in \mathbb{J}$	The discharge efficiency of EV j
$P_G^{max}(i)$	$i \in \mathbb{I}$	Maximum power from the external power grid at time-step i
CP		Contract Power value
$C_G^{buy}(i, CP)$	$i \in \mathbb{I}$	Cost of electricity purchased from the external power grid in i -th time-step
$C_G^{sell}(i)$	$i \in \mathbb{I}$	Cost of electricity sold to the external power grid in i -th time-step

Table 3: Case II: Decision variables.

Variable	Domain	Index	Description
$\alpha_{EV}(i, j)$	$\{0, 1\}$	$i \in \mathbb{I}, j \in \mathbb{J}$	Binary variable that represents EV $_j$ charging process in period i
$\beta_{EV}(i, j)$	$\{0, 1\}$	$i \in \mathbb{I}, j \in \mathbb{J}$	Binary variable that represents EV $_j$ discharging process in period i
$S_{EV}(i, j)$	\mathbb{R}_0^+	$i \in \mathbb{I}, j \in \mathbb{J}$	SoC of the EV j at the start of period $[T_{EV}^{in}, T_{EV}^{out}]$
$P_{M \rightarrow G}(i)$	\mathbb{R}_0^+	$i \in \mathbb{I}$	Power from manager to the grid in period i
$P_{G \rightarrow M}(i)$	\mathbb{R}_0^+	$i \in \mathbb{I}$	Power from the grid to manager in period i
$P_{M \rightarrow EV}(i, j)$	\mathbb{R}_0^+	$i \in \mathbb{I}, j \in \mathbb{J}$	Power from manager to j EV in period i

Figure 1: j -th EV exit and arrival times and main parameters.

In Table 3, the charging/discharging state of j -th EV is defined by $\alpha_{EV}(i, j)$ and $\beta_{EV}(i, j)$ in i -th time-step. When the battery of j -th EV is discharging then the value of $\beta_{EV}(i, j) = 1$ ($\alpha_{EV}(i, j) = 1$ if it is charging) in time-step i . Moreover, if j -th EV is outside of the SB in time-step i , then the variable $S_{EV}(i, j)$ is meaningless and should not be considered in the model. On the other hand, as it can be seen in Table 1, the index i of $S_{EV}(i, j)$ is considered in \mathbb{I} . Indeed, for simplicity in presentation, it was considered that index $i \in \mathbb{I}$ for S_{EV} and this issue will be taken into account in the objective function and constraints.

Objective Function

The main goal of this paper is to minimize the electricity bill of the entire building. The total cost of electricity for the building comprises the portion regarding CP, energy consumption, and other fees. The total cost from the power network is based on the energy cost that is transferred by the power grid to the building (through building managing entity), using a bi-hourly tariff (electricity tariff has 2 different values depending on time-of-use) and the surplus electricity can be sale to the external power grid (managed by the third party: building manager, aggregator, etc.), with a certain tariff rate. In this regard, the following objective function is considered:

$$\min \mathcal{J} = \text{SCP}(\text{CP}) + \sum_{i \in \mathbb{I}} C_G^{\text{buy}}(i, \text{CP}) P_{G \rightarrow M}(i) - \sum_{i \in \mathbb{I}} C_G^{\text{sell}}(i) P_{M \rightarrow G}(i) \quad (1)$$

where, $\text{SCP}(\text{CP})$ is a cost that is dependent on the value of the residential building contract power.

Constraints

In what follows, the constraints that should be considered in the proposed MBLP model are presented. These constraints are required to ensure that the physical limits of the resources and problem assumptions are not violated.

EVs constraints

In general, the EVs constraints are briefly formulated as follows:

$$0 \leq S_{\text{EV}}(i, j) \leq S_{\text{EV}}^{\text{max}}(j), \quad i \in \mathbb{I}, \quad j \in \mathbb{J}, \quad (2)$$

$$S_{\text{EV}}(T_{\text{EV}}^{\text{in}}((d, j) - 1), j) = S_{\text{EV}}^{\text{initial}}(d, j), \quad j \in \mathbb{J}, d \in \{0\} \cup \mathbb{D}, \quad (3)$$

$$P_{\text{M} \rightarrow \text{EV}}(i, j) \leq \alpha_{\text{EV}}(i, j) P_{\text{EV}}^{\text{ch}}(j) \tau, \quad i \in \mathbb{I}, \quad j \in \mathbb{J}, \quad (4)$$

$$P_{\text{EV} \rightarrow \text{M}}(i, j) \leq \beta_{\text{EV}}(i, j) P_{\text{EV}}^{\text{diss}}(j) \tau, \quad i \in \mathbb{I}, \quad j \in \mathbb{J}, \quad (5)$$

$$S_{\text{EV}}(i + 1, j) = S_{\text{EV}}(i, j) + \left[P_{\text{M} \rightarrow \text{EV}}(i, j) E_{\text{EV}}^{\text{ch}} - P_{\text{EV} \rightarrow \text{M}}(i, j) / E_{\text{EV}}^{\text{diss}} \right], \quad (6)$$

$$j \in \mathbb{J}, d \in \{0\} \cup \mathbb{D}, i = T_{\text{EV}}^{\text{in}}(d, j) - 1, \dots, T_{\text{EV}}^{\text{out}}(d + 1, j) - 2,$$

$$S_{\text{EV}}(T_{\text{EV}}^{\text{out}}(d, j) - 1, j) \geq S_{\text{EV}}^{\text{min-out}}(j), \quad j \in \mathbb{J}, \quad d \in \mathbb{D}, \quad (7)$$

$$S_{\text{EV}}(i, j) = 0, \quad j \in \mathbb{J}, d \in \mathbb{D}, i = T_{\text{EV}}^{\text{out}}(d, j), \dots, T_{\text{EV}}^{\text{in}}((d + 1, j) - 2), \quad (8)$$

$$\alpha_{\text{EV}}(i, j) + \beta_{\text{EV}}(i, j) \leq 1, \quad i \in \mathbb{I}, \quad j \in \mathbb{J}. \quad (9)$$

Here, Equation (2) presents the capacity constraints of j -th EV's battery. It was considered the constraints (3) to show the value of the initial charge of j -th EV at the arrival time $T_{\text{EV}}^{\text{in}}(d, j)$ in each day d . The consumed electricity from external power grid to charge EVs satisfies in constraint (4) and the obtained power by discharging EVs satisfies in constraint (5). Note that in equation (4), if $\alpha_{\text{EV}}(i, j) = 0$, then manager does not charge EV j in time-step i . And if $\alpha_{\text{EV}}(i, j) = 1$, then EV j could be charged by the managing entity at most $P_{\text{EV}}^{\text{ch}}(j) \tau$ in time-step i . Due to the charging or discharging process, the SoC of EVs may be changed. So, the updated equation of SoC is presented in constraint (6). The minimum allowable SoC for j -th EV at the departure time is $S_{\text{EV}}^{\text{min-out}}(j)$. In this respect, constraint (7) is considered at the departure time-steps. In day $d \in \mathbb{D}$, in time-steps $i = T_{\text{EV}}^{\text{out}}(i, j), \dots, T_{\text{EV}}^{\text{in}}(i, j) - 1$, EV j is not in the parking. In these time-steps, the charging and discharging operations should not occur. Accordingly, it was considered the constraints (8) in the mentioned time-steps. Finally, the constraints (9) guarantees that the EVs charging and discharging process do not occur at the same time. Note that, If any tenant (j) does not have an EV, it is possible to consider it in the model by $S_{\text{EV}}^{\text{max}}(j) = 0$.

Power Generation constraints

To ensure the power balance in each period $i \in \mathbb{I}$, the following mathematical formulation should be considered:

$$P_{\text{G} \rightarrow \text{M}}(i) + \sum_{j \in \mathbb{J}} P_{\text{EV} \rightarrow \text{M}}(i, j) + \sum_{j \in \mathbb{J}} P_{\text{PV}}(i, j) = P_{\text{M} \rightarrow \text{G}}(i) + \sum_{j \in \mathbb{J}} P_{\text{A}}(i, j) + \sum_{j \in \mathbb{J}} P_{\text{M} \rightarrow \text{EV}}(i, j) + P_{\text{C}}(i), \quad i \in \mathbb{I}. \quad (10)$$

As can be seen in equation (10), this equation is composed of the power that is required by the managing entity to supply the load demand of each apartment, the common services, and charging the EVs as well. It is also considered the generated power by PV panels and the EVs discharging process.

The following restrictions depict the cases when the building consumes electricity from the external power grid or injects electricity from the building to the external power network:

$$P_{\text{G} \rightarrow \text{M}}(i) \leq \text{CP}, \quad i \in \mathbb{I}, \quad (11)$$

$$P_{\text{M} \rightarrow \text{G}}(i) \leq \frac{1}{2} \text{CP}, \quad i \in \mathbb{I}. \quad (12)$$

(b) Step (ii) of Case II

After step (i) is finished and the total electricity cost of the building is obtained, as well as per each time-slot i , the power cost of the building at time-slot i is c_i , where $c_i > 0$ means that the building get power from the external power grid and should spend c_i Euro for this consumption. In contrast, $c_i < 0$ means that the

Table 4: Parameters of the BESS.

Parameter	Index	Description
S_{BE}^{\max}		Maximum State of Charge(SoC) for BESS
S_{BE}^{initial}		Initial State of Charge(SoC) for BESS at the beginning of time-period
S_{BE}^{\min}		Minimum State of Charge(SoC) for BESS
$P_{BE}^{\text{ch}}(i)$	$i \in \mathbb{I}$	Active power related to the charging process of the BESS in period i
$P_{BE}^{\text{diss}}(i)$	$i \in \mathbb{I}$	Active power related to the discharging process of BESS in period i
E_{BE}^{ch}		The charge efficiency of BESS
E_{BE}^{diss}		The discharge efficiency of BESS

building sells electricity to the grid and gain $|c_i|$ Euro for this power injection. Now, the building manager should determine the share of each apartment from c_i . Indeed, the manager entity should design a tariff for dividing c_i among the apartments and determine the selling price or buying energy in time-slot i .

Therefore, $d(i, j) = P_A(i, j) + P_{M \rightarrow EV}(i, j) - P_{PV}(i, j) - P_{EV \rightarrow M}(i, j)$ is the generated/consumed power by apartment j and its PV/EV at time-slot i . $d(i, j) > 0$ means that j th apartment consume energy. On the other hand, $d(i, j) < 0$ means that apartment j produce energy and inject to the grid. Then, it is considered two cases $d(i, j) > 0$ and $d(i, j) < 0$. In the case $d(i, j) > 0$, the price of selling/buying electricity to/from manager is considered as $C_G^{\text{buy}}(i, CP)$. Accordingly, the electricity cost of apartment j at time-slot i is $d(i, j)C_G^{\text{buy}}(i, cp)$. In the case $d(i, j) < 0$, it is considered that $C_G^{\text{sell}}(i)$ for selling/buying to/from the manager and the share of apartment j is $d(i, j)C_G^{\text{sell}}(i)$.

4.3. Case III: Smart Management with a Single Contract Power and using BESS (SMSCP B)

In the proposed SMSCP B case, the following points are considered:

- An external entity (manager entity, aggregator, electricity supplier, etc.) is considered to manage all building energy resources;
- The generated renewable energy from PVs panels is managed among apartments;
- The EVs charging/discharging process is managed by the manager entity;
- The battery of an EV can charge/discharge from/to its corresponding apartment;
- A BESS is used in this case III.

The main goal of the case SMSCP B is to present a building resources scheduling solution, such that the load demand of the residential buildings is fulfilled and electricity cost minimized.

4.3.1. Mathematical Model of Case III

In this Case III, the use of a battery energy storage system is proposed. Then, the following parameters and decision variables are added to the considered parameters and variables in Tables 2 and 3.

Now, the constraints presented in (10) should be replaced by the following constraints:

$$P_{G \rightarrow M}(i) + \sum_{j \in J} P_{EV \rightarrow M}(i, j) + \sum_{j \in J} P_{PV}(i, j) + P_{BE \rightarrow M} = P_{M \rightarrow G}(i) + \sum_{j \in J} P_A(i, j) + \sum_{j \in J} P_{M \rightarrow EV}(i, j) + P_{M \rightarrow BE} + P_C(i), \quad i \in \mathbb{I}. \quad (13)$$

Table 5: Decision variables of the BESS

Variable	Domain	Index	Description
$\alpha_{\text{BE}}(i)$	$\{0,1\}$	$i \in \mathbb{I}$	Binary variable that represents the BESS charging process in period i
$\beta_{\text{BE}}(i)$	$\{0,1\}$	$i \in \mathbb{I}$	Binary variable that represents the BESS discharging process in period i
$S_{\text{BE}}(i)$	\mathbb{R}_0^+	$i \in \mathbb{I}$	SoC of the BESS at the start of period i
$P_{\text{M} \rightarrow \text{BE}}(i)$	\mathbb{R}_0^+	$i \in \mathbb{I}$	Power from manager to BESS in period i
$P_{\text{BE} \rightarrow \text{M}}(i)$	\mathbb{R}_0^+	$i \in \mathbb{I}$	Power from BESS to manager in period i

Moreover, the following constraints are added to the proposed constraints of Case II.

$$S_{\text{BE}}^{\min} \leq S_{\text{BE}}(i) \leq S_{\text{BE}}^{\max}, \quad i \in \mathbb{I}, \quad (14)$$

$$S_{\text{BE}}(0) = S_{\text{BE}}^{\text{initial}}, \quad (15)$$

$$P_{\text{M} \rightarrow \text{BE}}(i) \leq \alpha_{\text{BE}}(i) P_{\text{BE}}^{\text{ch}} \tau, \quad i \in \mathbb{I}, \quad (16)$$

$$P_{\text{BE} \rightarrow \text{M}}(i, j) \leq \beta_{\text{BE}}(i, j) P_{\text{BE}}^{\text{diss}} \tau, \quad i \in \mathbb{I}, \quad (17)$$

$$S_{\text{BE}}(i+1) = S_{\text{BE}}(i) + \left[P_{\text{M} \rightarrow \text{BE}}(i) E_{\text{BE}}^{\text{ch}} - P_{\text{BE} \rightarrow \text{M}}(i) / E_{\text{BE}}^{\text{diss}} \right], \quad i \in \mathbb{I}, \quad (18)$$

$$\alpha_{\text{BE}}(i) + \beta_{\text{BE}}(i) \leq 1, \quad i \in \mathbb{I}. \quad (19)$$

Similar to EVs constraints, Equation (14) presents the BESS capacity constraints, and (15) shows the initial value of BESS in $i = 0$. The transferred power from management to charge BESS satisfies in constraint (16) and the obtained power by discharging of BESS satisfies in constraint (17). If $\alpha_{\text{BE}}(i) = 0$, then the manager does not charge BESS in time-step i . And if $\alpha_{\text{BE}}(i) = 1$, then BESS could be charged at most $P_{\text{BE}}^{\text{ch}} \tau$ in time-step i by the manager. The SoC of BESS is changed in each time-slot by the charging or discharging process that is presented in constraint (18). The constraint (19) is considered to show that the BESS charging and discharging process of BESS should not occur at the same time-steps.

Finally, the mathematical model of the proposed problem in Case SMSCPB is summarized as following Mixed Binary Mathematical Model:

$$\text{Minimize } \mathcal{J} = \text{SCP}(\text{CP}) + \sum_{i \in \mathbb{I}} C_G^{\text{buy}}(i, \text{CP}) P_{\text{G} \rightarrow \text{M}}(i) - \sum_{i \in \mathbb{I}} C_G^{\text{sell}}(i) P_{\text{M} \rightarrow \text{G}}(i) \quad (20\text{a})$$

$$\text{S.t. } 0 \leq S_{\text{EV}}(i, j) \leq S_{\text{EV}}^{\text{max}}(j), \quad i \in \mathbb{I}, \quad j \in \mathbb{J}, \quad (20\text{b})$$

$$S_{\text{EV}}(T_{\text{EV}}^{\text{in}}((d, j) - 1), j) = S_{\text{EV}}^{\text{initial}}(d, j), \quad j \in \mathbb{J}, d \in \{0\} \cup \mathbb{D}, \quad (20\text{c})$$

$$P_{\text{M} \rightarrow \text{EV}}(i, j) \leq \alpha_{\text{EV}}(i, j) P_{\text{EV}}^{\text{ch}}(j) \tau, \quad i \in \mathbb{I}, \quad j \in \mathbb{J}, \quad (20\text{d})$$

$$P_{\text{EV} \rightarrow \text{M}}(i, j) \leq \beta_{\text{EV}}(i, j) P_{\text{EV}}^{\text{diss}}(j) \tau, \quad i \in \mathbb{I}, \quad j \in \mathbb{J}, \quad (20\text{e})$$

$$S_{\text{EV}}(i + 1, j) = S_{\text{EV}}(i, j) + \left[P_{\text{M} \rightarrow \text{EV}}(i, j) E_{\text{EV}}^{\text{ch}} - P_{\text{EV} \rightarrow \text{M}}(i, j) / E_{\text{EV}}^{\text{diss}} \right], \quad (20\text{f})$$

$$j \in \mathbb{J}, d \in \{0\} \cup \mathbb{D}, i = T_{\text{EV}}^{\text{in}}(d, j) - 1, \dots, T_{\text{EV}}^{\text{out}}(d + 1, j) - 2,$$

$$S_{\text{EV}}(T_{\text{EV}}^{\text{out}}(d, j) - 1, j) \geq S_{\text{EV}}^{\text{min.out}}(j), \quad j \in \mathbb{J}, \quad d \in \mathbb{D}, \quad (20\text{g})$$

$$S_{\text{EV}}(i, j) = 0, \quad j \in \mathbb{J}, d \in \mathbb{D}, i = T_{\text{EV}}^{\text{out}}(d, j), \dots, T_{\text{EV}}^{\text{in}}((d + 1, j) - 2, \quad (20\text{h})$$

$$\alpha_{\text{EV}}(i, j) + \beta_{\text{EV}}(i, j) \leq 1, \quad i \in \mathbb{I}, \quad j \in \mathbb{J}. \quad (20\text{i})$$

$$S_{\text{BE}}^{\text{min}} \leq S_{\text{BE}}(i) \leq S_{\text{BE}}^{\text{max}}, \quad i \in \mathbb{I}, \quad (20\text{j})$$

$$S_{\text{BE}}(0) = S_{\text{BE}}^{\text{initial}}, \quad (20\text{k})$$

$$P_{\text{M} \rightarrow \text{BE}}(i) \leq \alpha_{\text{BE}}(i) P_{\text{BE}}^{\text{ch}} \tau, \quad i \in \mathbb{I}, \quad (20\text{l})$$

$$P_{\text{BE} \rightarrow \text{M}}(i, j) \leq \beta_{\text{BE}}(i, j) P_{\text{BE}}^{\text{diss}} \tau, \quad i \in \mathbb{I}, \quad (20\text{m})$$

$$S_{\text{BE}}(i + 1) = S_{\text{BE}}(i) + \left[P_{\text{M} \rightarrow \text{BE}}(i) E_{\text{BE}}^{\text{ch}} - P_{\text{BE} \rightarrow \text{M}}(i) / E_{\text{BE}}^{\text{diss}} \right], \quad i = 0, \dots, I, \quad (20\text{n})$$

$$\alpha_{\text{BE}}(i) + \beta_{\text{BE}}(i) \leq 1, \quad i \in \mathbb{I}, \quad (20\text{o})$$

$$P_{\text{G} \rightarrow \text{M}}(i) + \sum_{j \in \mathbb{J}} P_{\text{EV} \rightarrow \text{M}}(i, j) + \sum_{j \in \mathbb{J}} P_{\text{PV}}(i, j) + P_{\text{BE} \rightarrow \text{M}} = \quad (20\text{p})$$

$$P_{\text{M} \rightarrow \text{G}}(i) + \sum_{j \in \mathbb{J}} P_{\text{A}}(i, j) + \sum_{j \in \mathbb{J}} P_{\text{M} \rightarrow \text{EV}}(i, j) + P_{\text{M} \rightarrow \text{BE}} + P_{\text{C}}(i), \quad i \in \mathbb{I},$$

$$P_{\text{G} \rightarrow \text{M}}(i) \leq \text{CP}, \quad i \in \mathbb{I}, \quad (20\text{q})$$

$$P_{\text{M} \rightarrow \text{G}}(i) \leq \frac{1}{2} \text{CP}, \quad i \in \mathbb{I}. \quad (20\text{r})$$

We recall that the decision variables of the above model are presented in Tables 3 and 5. According to these tables, the number of decision variables, for I days and J apartment, is $(7 + 4J)I$.

310 5. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, a real database of a residential building containing 15 apartments is considered in which six of them have 6.9 kVA of contract power value, six apartments with 10.35 kVA, and three with 13.8 kVA. Each apartment has one electrical vehicle and one PV generation panel with a capacity of 3.6 kW. The value of the mentioned parameters in the model, such as power demanded value from apartments (P_{A}), and common services (P_{C}), the PVs generated power (P_{PV}), and arrival/departure time of EVs ($T_{\text{EV}}^{\text{in}}/T_{\text{EV}}^{\text{out}}$) are recorded every 15 minutes. 315

5.1. Case study

There are always problems with databases, which is required a data pre-processing phase to “clean” the database. It was identified that some recorded data were missed. To fill in the lack of data values, and in this way, to enable the use of the database for study, a regression model and an adjacent interpolation approach were implemented. 320

Table 6: Case I: Electricity consumption and costs results

BU(CP) ...(kVA)	Off-Peak hour Con. (kWh)	Peak hours Con. (kWh)	Total BU Con. (kWh)	Total EV Con. (kWh)	Total PV gen. (kWh)	Total Con. (kWh)	Max load (kW)	Total Price (EUR)
1 (6.9)	+ 652.07	+ 3158.27	+ 3810.34	+ 5292.91	- 2443.40	6659.84	2.02	1037.89
2 (6.9)	+ 786.73	+ 2812.53	+ 3599.27	+ 5681.69	- 2168.72	7112.24	2.72	1085.89
3 (6.9)	+ 970.85	+ 3223.04	+ 4193.90	+ 5406.77	- 3004.60	6596.06	2.70	1002.80
4 (6.9)	+ 2551.92	+10,807.99	+13,359.91	+ 5272.41	- 2443.42	16,188.90	4.65	2379.15
5 (6.9)	+ 1416.06	+ 4186.99	+ 5603.05	+ 5466.44	- 2166.52	8902.96	3.11	1327.95
6 (6.9)	+ 2670.14	+ 9509.36	+12,179.50	+ 5052.19	- 3006.77	14,224.92	3.89	2071.25
7 (10.35)	+ 2183.67	+ 6706.56	+ 8890.24	+ 5095.57	- 2442.72	11,543.08	3.63	1785.84
8 (10.35)	+ 1152.06	+ 5634.61	+ 6786.68	+ 5146.80	- 2168.86	9764.62	2.94	1578.93
9 (10.35)	+ 3021.72	+ 7527.77	+10,549.50	+ 5205.44	- 3004.65	12,750.29	4.22	1910.32
10 (10.35)	+ 5013.69	+27,738.39	+32,752.08	+ 5222.01	- 2443.28	35,530.81	6.38	5419.85
11 (10.35)	+ 4285.09	+13,684.58	+17,969.67	+ 5184.77	- 2169.73	20,984.71	3.96	3131.20
12 (10.35)	+ 1768.63	+ 5878.99	+ 7647.63	+ 5390.54	- 3004.94	10,033.23	3.34	1562.00
13 (13.8)	+ 5770.40	+16,889.10	+22,659.50	+ 5459.00	- 2442.97	25,675.54	4.44	3806.35
14 (13.8)	+ 2925.64	+18,565.46	+21,491.10	+ 5045.78	- 2168.50	24,368.38	4.63	38,56.64
15 (13.8)	+ 1394.74	+12,613.22	+14,007.96	+ 5434.44	- 3004.96	16,437.45	2.83	2689.03
C.S(13.8)	+ 3195.69	+16,962.33	+20,158.02	+ 0.00	- 3004.94	17,153.07	1.25	3156.23
SUM:	+39,759.17	+16,5899.24	+20,5658.42	+79,356.83	-41,089.08	26,4084.20	56.78	37,801.39
BU: Building Unit								

The time-slot in this case study is one year and $\tau = 15$ minutes. In this way, each day is divided to $24 \times 4 = 96$ time-steps and consequently, the time-period contains $I = 96 * 365 = 35,040.00$ time-steps.

An annual bi-hourly tariff was used, i.e. the electricity price is reduced in the night or the weekend and higher in the remaining periods. However, this proposed model (20) is a general model that can be used for others databases.

Moreover, as already mentioned, it was assumed that each apartment has one EV with the following characteristics:

$$S_{EV}^{\max} = 27.2 \text{ (kWh)}, \quad P_{EV}^{\text{ch}} = 3.7 \text{ (kW)}, \quad P_{EV}^{\text{diss}} = 3.33 \text{ (kW)}. \quad (21)$$

Besides, the initial SoC of EVs at the arrival time $S_{EV}^{\text{initial}}(j)$ is set randomly.

5.2. Results of Case I

Case I is considered as a “reference case” study and the results of Case II and III are compared with this case. In this case, no optimization is needed and the total consumption costs are obtained by simple calculating. The obtained results are reported in Table 6 and Figure 3.

Note that in Table 6 the positive sign refers to the electrical energy that is consumed and the negative sign concerns the electrical energy that is produced.

For better vision, the results for apartment 10 are reported in figure 2. As it can be seen in Figure 2, the distance between the contract power (13.8 kW) and maximum peak load (6.38 kW) is significant, suggesting that the contract power value is overvalued for this apartment. Analyzing Table 6, this fact is concluded for other apartments too. These results show that the current CPs are not chosen properly and as a result, the electricity bill of each apartment (the last column of the table) it becomes unnecessarily more expensive.

In Figure 3, the electrical energy consumption from the external power grid, the generated power by PVs, the total consumption of apartments, common services consumption, and the used energy for charging EVs are plotted for three days (July 17-19).

5.3. Results of Case II

As mentioned in case II, a single CP for the entire residential building and EVs discharging process were considered to reduce the electricity bill of the smart building. In this case, an MBLP proposed in 4.2.1 was solved. In this model, the building CP should be selected taking into consideration the optimization results.

Figure 2: Case I: Annual electricity consumption/CP value (apartment 10)

Figure 3: Case I: Building energy resources results)

Table 7: Case II: Annual electricity costs and peak load results.

CP Value (kW)	Total Cost(EUR)	Max Load(kW)
13.8	Infeasible	
17.25	19,882.49	17.25
20.70	19,536.62	20.70
27.60	19,496.96	23.54
34.50	54,433.39	24.54
41.40	54,544.20	24.85

Figure 4: Case II: Energy resources management results for $CP = 27.6$ (kW)

There are six different choices for CP value (Table 10). The MBLP was solved with these CPs and the results, including total annual cost and max load of the building, are reported in Table 10.

350 The results in Table 10 shows that the optimal CP value for case II is $CP = 27.6$ (kW). The obtain results corresponding to $CP = 27.6$ (kW) are reported in Figure 4.

As shown in Figure 4, EVs are charged from the external power grid mainly during the low demand time and they are discharged when it is verified high demand time to minimize the consumed power from the external power grid. As a result, at the high demand times, the need for power is reduced and becoming, in fact, low demand times. This point leads to a 43.7% reduction of the total cost in comparison with Case I.

5.4. Results of Case III

We recall that in Case III, to decrease the total electricity consumption cost, the residential building is equipped with a BESS. Therefore, a BESS with the following characteristics is considered:

$$S_{BE}^{\max} = 50 \text{ (kWh)}, \quad P_{BE}^{\text{ch}} = 6.3 \text{ (kW)}, \quad P_{BE}^{\text{diss}} = 5.67 \text{ (kW)}. \quad (22)$$

360 The initial state of charge (SoC) is considered as $S_{BE}^{\text{initial}} = 0$ and the initial SoC of EVs at the arrival time $S_{EV}^{\text{initial}}(j)$ are set randomly.

In the beginning, similar to what was done in Case II, the optimal CP value is determined. In Table 8, the value of annual electricity cost for different values of CP is reported.

It can be seen in Table 8 that the optimal residential building contract power value for Case III is $CP = 20.7$ kW. The obtain results corresponding to $CP = 20.7$ kW are reported in Figure 5.

365 Figure 5 shows the performance and impact of the BESS usage in smoothing the building power consumption. Based on this Figure, The BESS stores the surplus power mainly at the low load demand periods and discharge it when it is verified an increase of the collective load demand. It should be noted that, due to the performance and management of BESS, the residential building CP value is reduced from $CP = 27.6$ kW to $CP = 20.7$ kW.

370 In final, by following step (b), the obtained annual electricity costs of the apartments, in Cases I, II, and III are reported in Table 9. According to this table, Case II in comparison with Case I, a significant reduction in the electricity cost of each apartment has occurred. Moreover, in Case III, the total cost value has been reduced by 6.3%, in comparison of Case II, and 47% reduction in comparison with Case I.

Table 8: Case III: Annual electricity costs and peak load results.

CP Value (kW)	Total Cost (EUR)	Max Load (kW)
13.8	19,463.57	13.80
17.25	18,282.58	17.25
20.70	18,162.33	20.70
27.60	53,348.14	24.31
34.50	53,458.99	25.93
41.40	53,569.80	24.65

Figure 5: Case III: Energy resources management results for $CP = 20.7$ (kW)

Table 9: Comparison of the annual bill

Apartments	Total Cost of Case III (CP=20.7) (EUR)	Total Cost of Case II (CP=27.6) (EUR)	Total Cost of Case I (EUR)
1	470.10	400.79	1037.89
2	528.54	454.65	1085.89
3	438.68	359.31	1002.80
4	1442.91	1520.07	2379.15
5	616.58	617.90	1327.95
6	1221.87	1249.43	2071.25
7	921.52	912.73	1785.84
8	786.94	759.30	1578.93
9	949.19	932.09	1910.32
10	3326.31	3818.32	5419.85
11	1637.58	1854.01	3131.20
12	716.51	714.65	1562.01
13	1959.12	2253.67	3806.35
14	1747.72	2053.82	3856.64
15	1398.68	1596.17	2689.03
Electricity Bill of SB	18,162.33	19,496.96	34,645.15

Table 10: Results comparison of proposed model with Reference [17]

	Total Cost Case III(EUR)	Total Cost Case II (EUR)	Total Cost Case I (EUR)
Proposed Model	18,339.77	19,496.96	34,645.15
Reference [17]	39,234.90	43,502.82	58,892.19

The efficiency of the proposed model is presented in Table 10 by comparing the obtained results with Reference [17], which neither took into account the intelligent energy management system nor the optimal contract power capacity.

The results in Table 10 indicate a significant reduction in the building total costs. Indeed, the total consumption cost of the residential building has been reduced by around 55% in comparison with the reference case study [17].

In summary, this work proposed a new intelligent energy management system to manage the building energy resources for multi-apartment buildings, by considering a single contract power for the whole building, instead of each private facility. The obtained results show a significant reduction in total cost by founding the optimal contract power capacity.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

The main goal of this paper was to minimize the electricity consumption costs of a collective residential building. The electricity cost contains a portion regarding contract power value, active electrical energy consumption, and governmental rates. As the governmental rates are fixed, the proposed approaches took only into consideration the contracted power value and electrical energy consumption. Three following points were proposed and considered to reduce each part of the electricity bill:

- The flexibility in contract power capacity was assumed for each unit and, therefore, the collective residential building has a single contract power;
- The charging and discharging process of the Electrical Vehicles (EVs) and also Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) was considered to reduce the electrical energy costs;
- A building energy manager entity (aggregator, electricity supplier, etc.) was considered to manage all the building energy resources to minimize the total electricity bill.

To investigate the efficiency of the proposed approach, three case studies were formulated:

1. The electricity costs of the residential building were achieved without considering energy management system, single contract power, BESS, and discharging process of the EVs;
2. Smart management with a single contract power is considered, without BESS usage;
3. Smart management with a single contract power is considered, with BESS usage.

The problem was successfully formulated by a mixed binary linear programming model, taking into consideration a real database concerning load consumption, photovoltaic generation, and information about the characteristic of EVs and BESS. In the proposed model: a) not only the schedule of charging and discharging process of EVs and BESS were optimized, b) but also the optimal single contract power value was determined, and c) the electricity bill of the smart building was significantly reduced. The obtained results showed promising insofar as cost reduction was obtained in the order of 47% when compared to the case in which there is no energy resources management or consideration of flexible contracted power. For future work, the authors would like to explore the incorporation of demand response programs in the proposed models and also to study the economic viability of the proposed approach.

7. Author Contributions

410 Conceptualization, Z.F., S.R. and, J.S.; methodology, Z.F., J.S., and S.R.; data curation, M.D.; formal analysis, Z.F. and S.R.; funding acquisition, S.R. and J.S.; investigation, Z.F.; validation, Z.V., S.R.; supervision, Z.V. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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9. Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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